

THE ROLE OF LEADERSHIP SKILLS IN RAISING A SPIRITUALLY MATURE GENERATION

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Abstract. This article discusses about organizational skills and highlights the role and importance of leadership skills in raising a spiritually mature young generation. The purpose of the scientific work is to shed light on the role of organizational ability in the educational process and the essence of leadership and types of leadership in achieving spiritual maturity.

Keywords: leadership, teaching process, directive leadership, democratic leadership, liberal leadership, feedback, educational leadership, academic success, high standards.

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится об организаторских способностях и подчеркивается роль и значение лидерских качеств в воспитании духовно зрелого молодого поколения. Цель научной работы – пролить свет на роль организаторских способностей в образовательном процессе, на сущность лидерства и виды лидерства в достижении духовной зрелости.

Ключевые слова: лидерство, учебный процесс, директивное лидерство, демократическое лидерство, либеральное лидерство, обратная связь, образовательное лидерство, академические успехи, высокие стандарты.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tashkilotchilik qobiliyati haqida so‘z yuritilib, ma’naviy yetuk yosh avlodni tarbiyalashda yetakchilik qobiliyatining o‘rni va ahamiyati yoritilgan. Ilmiy ishning maqsadi ma’naviy kamolotga erishishda tashkilotchilik qobiliyatining o‘rni va yetakchilik mohiyati va yetakchilik turlarini yoritishdan iborat.

Kalit so‘zlar: yetakchilik, o‘qitish jarayoni, direktiv yetakchilik, demokratik yetakchilik, liberal yetakchilik, fikr-mulohazalar, ta’lim yetakchiligi, akademik muvaffaqiyat, yuqori standartlar.

Leadership is an important factor affecting the overall effectiveness and success of education. Different leadership styles have different effects on people's behavior, group culture and ultimately the achievement of goals. "Leadership means never forgetting the why, the ethics of the purpose, and all those people—teachers and students—who have put their trust in you," said one leader. "Leadership is never believing your own press." Leigh Patel (2018) stated that a modest stewardship of learning is the first and most important quality of educational leadership. We have plenty of highly compensated leaders in education right now, but they tend to talk more about innovation than learning and even less about the patterns of denied access to education at the population level. Leadership in education must be able to acknowledge the legacies and flaws of individualistic, Eurocentric frameworks of human development that exist for the sake of success and dominance.

To quote Ken Lindblom Leadership in education entails continuously keeping the pupils' learning as the only objective. An education leader will always stay focused on the right things if they keep that at the forefront of their minds. It entails being current with organizational theory, content theory, and instructional theory. It refers to inspiring and instructing. It entails resisting disruptive, even hostile, external pressures and encouraging societal change that will improve learning for all kids. It entails promoting student learning both internally and externally.

It entails doing all possible to make sure that every student has everything they require) in order to learn as well as possible. It entails supplying a professional environment that enables—and obliges—teachers to carry out the actions they believe are best for students' learning, including the freedom to disregard anything that might get in the way of that learning, if necessary.

Good educational leadership is important because schools constantly seek to enhance their operations and give students the best education possible. Surprisingly, a large number of individuals participating in their community's educational system are unsure of what constitutes educational leadership. Education leadership is a process that combines the efforts, skills, and expertise of educators, parents, and educators with the aim of enhancing not only the standard of instruction but also the educational system as a whole.

Understanding the role of leadership styles in shaping education is essential for managers and future personnel seeking to improve their effectiveness and optimize their approach to leadership.

Directive leadership is a style of leadership characterized by clear, precise instructions and instructions from the leader to his subordinates. In this approach, leaders take responsibility for decision-making, set goals, delegate tasks, and closely monitor the work of team members. A leader communicates clear expectations, gives clear instructions, and closely monitors the progress and performance of individuals or a group. Directive leadership can be effective in situations that require quick decision making, a clear chain of command, and a structured work environment. However, it may not be appropriate in contexts that require creativity, autonomy, and empowerment of team members.

Democratic leadership is characterized by the participation of team members in decision-making processes. In this approach, the leader values open communication, diversity of views, and encourages cooperation within the group. By empowering team members to contribute ideas, democratic leaders foster creativity, engagement, and ownership among people. Democratic leaders believe in the importance of equality and respect, and value the contributions of all team members, regardless of their position or hierarchy. They actively seek and consider different opinions and encourage healthy debate to make the most informed decisions. This leadership style promotes a collaborative and inclusive environment that leads to higher levels of job satisfaction and motivation among team members. One of the main advantages of democratic leadership is the ability to use the wisdom and experience of the team.

By involving individuals in the decision-making process, leaders can tap into the diverse skills and perspectives available in the group, resulting in more innovative and effective decisions. In addition, this approach encourages accountability and instills a sense of responsibility in team members who are actively involved in shaping results. However, democratic leadership also has its limitations. The decision-making process can be time-consuming because it requires gathering and weighing multiple viewpoints. A directive leadership style may be more appropriate when solving problems that require quick action or are highly specialized.

Liberal leadership refers to a style of legal governance that fosters individual freedoms, social equality, and a progressive culture. Liberal leaders typically prioritize civil rights, environmental protection, inclusive societies, and economic prosperity. They support democratic institutions, human rights and the rule of law. Liberal leadership values diversity and encourages open communication, seeking to find common ground and build consensus. It has a strong focus on evidence-based decision-making, scientific progress and innovation. Ultimately, liberal leadership seeks to create a fair and just society that promotes freedom, equality, and opportunity for all. Suggestions for improving the organization of leadership in companies:

1. Development of transparency and communication. developing an open and transparent communication channel between managers and executors. Regularly share company goals, strategies and progress updates to ensure stability and build trust in the organization,

2. Actively promote diversity and inclusion within the leadership team. Seeking and valuing diverse perspectives, experiences and expertise to improve decision-making processes and create a more inclusive work environment,

3. Lead by Example: Set the tone for effective leadership by demonstrating desired behaviors and values. Leaders must lead by example by demonstrating integrity, compassion and responsibility in their actions and decisions;

4. Receive feedback and adapt. Regularly seek feedback from both stakeholders to understand their perceptions of leadership effectiveness and areas for improvement in the organization.

The results highlight the need for effective leadership practices that align with group goals and promote employee engagement, motivation, and performance. By taking a transformational approach to leadership, leaders can inspire and empower their teams, creating a positive work environment that contributes to organizational success. Additionally, implementing strategies such as leadership development programs, feedback mechanisms, and fostering a culture of open communication and collaboration can contribute to overall improvement within an organization. It is critical that organizations prioritize leadership development and create the supports and opportunities to increase their chances of success in an ever-changing and competitive environment.

The major goal of educational leadership is to ensure academic success through improvements to procedures, instruction, and resources. Unfortunately, without the assistance and cooperation of all parties concerned, including the children, parents, instructors, decision-makers, and even the broader public, this achievement cannot be ensured or even achieved. Educational leadership is a way of quality actually works:

- establish a goal of achieving academic success for all children, regardless of socioeconomic status;
- strive to keep a responsive, safe, and healthy learning environment;
- assign accountability to everyone and enhance the curriculum and teaching strategies.

A strong teaching culture can be developed with the help of leadership in education. It may also affect how well students learn and perform. Effective leadership is widely seen as the foundation for significant changes in education.

Leaders must have a thorough understanding of pedagogy and engage in practice themselves in this effort to enhance learning within the school community. This collaborative

leadership approach puts the ego to one side and prioritizes others' needs over one's own. A great leader "must first serve others and that this simple fact is key to his or her greatness: true leadership arises from people whose first motive is a desire to help others," according to the servant leadership school of thought. Servant leaders in education uphold high standards while also assisting teachers and students in developing their abilities to achieve better. These leaders foster a desire for improvement while keeping an eye on both relationships and results. The ten traits of servant leaders, according to the previous president of the Robert K. Greenleaf Center for Servant Leadership, are: listening, empathy, healing, awareness, persuasion, conceptualization, foresight, stewardship, commitment to the growth of others, and fostering community. By removing obstacles, offering resources, and facilitating communication with the entire school community, servant leaders can develop high-performance teachers.

People frequently use leadership philosophies that are derived from their genetic makeup, personality, and social environments. This is not a bad thing; part of being a strong leader is understanding which leadership style naturally works the best for you. It's essential to establish a pliable style that incorporates many leadership strategies and can be adjusted to new situations as they arise in order to increase leadership effectiveness. Authoritarian leaders, often known as autocrats, construct a distinct vision of the final result and how to get there. They establish precise standards and unambiguous expectations. These leaders typically anticipate that their followers would follow their directives without question and without delay. Autocratic leaders don't always think of themselves as "know-it-all" who are superior to others. In fact, they frequently have a laser-like focus on attaining effective outcomes by predetermined activities that they feel are best for the company. Sometimes an authoritarian leader would consult a small circle of trusted peers before making a decision.

A growing amount of research demonstrates that teaching with instructional leadership do better than others. By enhancing teaching quality, this coaching leadership approach focuses on student learning outcomes. Planning, evaluating, coordinating, and improving teaching and learning are all practices of instructional leadership. Instructional leaders work closely with teachers to assess their performance and support their professional development through coaching and mentoring. To become an instructional leader, one must invest time in pedagogical problem-solving, take steps to enhance instructors' instruction, and hold teachers responsible for developing their instructional abilities. Great teaching processes are built on strong school leadership. According to the evidence, strong leadership is necessary to foster a climate in which every student can receive a high-quality education. Teachers who seek leadership in postgraduate education will be able to support successful teaching and learning practices, keep up with changes in the education sector, and introduce fresh ideas into classrooms. Everyone is aware of the importance of effective leadership for corporate success.

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